

A RARE CASE OF CD20-POSITIVE CUTANEOUS T-CELL LYMPHOMA

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ABSTRACT Primary cutaneous T-cell lymphomas (PTCLs) are defined as non-Hodgkin lymphomas in the skin with no evidence of extracutaneous involvement at the time of diagnosis. In the recent lymphoma classifications, PTCLs are further divided into cutaneous T-cell lymphoma (CTCL) and cutaneous B-cell lymphoma (CBCL). CTCL is a group of lymphoproliferative disorders characterized by the localization of the neoplastic T lymphocytes in the skin. CD20-positive CTCL is a rare condition that is associated with the co-expressions of CD20 and T-cell. CD20 is a marker that is commonly used in the investigation of B-cell to assist in differentiating T-cell and B-cell neoplasms. CD20-positive T-cell lymphoma is extremely rare with only fewer than 40 cases have been reported. In these cases, the skin involvement manifests as cutaneous plaques, nodules, or erythematous patches without predilection for specific locations.

We report a case of CD20-positive T-cell lymphoma in a 90-year-old woman. The diagnosis was established based on the history, physical examination, and histopathology examination supported by positive CD3 and CD20 staining on immunohistochemistry (IHC). The patient has treated with R-CHOP (Rituximab - cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, vincristine, and prednisone) regimen and showed significant clinical improvement after two cycles of chemotherapy.

KEYWORDS Cutaneous T-cell Lymphoma, CD20, CD3, R-CHOP

Introduction

Cutaneous T-cell lymphoma (CTCL) is a clonal proliferation of T or B lymphocytes and rarely NK cells or plasmacytoid dendritic cells which can involve the skin. Primary cutaneous peripheral T-cell lymphoma (PTCL) is defined as non-Hodgkin lymphoma on the skin without extracutaneous involvement. After gastrointestinal, skin is the second most common site of extranodal non-Hodgkin lymphoma, with an estimated annual incidence of 1/10,000 in Western countries. [1]

PTCL has different clinical manifestations and may progress to systemic lymphoma. Therefore, PTCL requires prompt treatment and multidisciplinary approach including dermatologist, pathologist, haematologist and radiation oncologist. In the latest classification of lymphoma, PTCL can be categorized into two different groups: cutaneous T-cell lymphoma (CTCL) and cutaneous B-cell lymphoma (CBCL). In Western countries, CTCL has an incidence of 75% -80% of all PTCL. Mycosis fungoides (MF) is the most common type and has an incidence of 20% -25%. [2], [3]

CD20 is a transmembrane protein with a molecular weight of 35 to 37 kD which is expressed early during B-cell development and disappeared during terminal B-cell differentiation into plasma cells. Its function is still unclear but is thought to act as a calcium channel in the cell membrane. CD20 is classified as a pan-B-cell marker, and its presence in benign and neoplastic lymphocytes is generally considered specific for cells originating from B-cell lineage. However, recent studies have shown that PTCL rarely expresses CD20, making the definitive diagnosis of CD20 lymphoma difficult. [4]

CD20-positive CTCL is a rare condition characterized by

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Fig.1.A.

Fig.1.B.

CD20 co-expression and T-cell markers such as CD3, CD5, or UCHL-11. Positive CD20 finding in T-cell lymphoma is a deviant immunophenotype although there are indicators of other T-cell markers. The diagnosis of primary cutaneous peripheral T-cell lymphoma not otherwise specified (PTCL-NOS) was made when the criteria of other CTCL subtypes are not met. The majority of CD20-positive CTCL cases is included in this subtype.[4] It is reported that this subtype is mostly seen in adult patients and presents as solitary, local or generalized nodules or tumours without specific predilection. Chemotherapy is the treatment of choice with a 5-year survival rate of less than 20%. [2],[3]

We report a rare case of a CD20-positive CTCL in a 90-year-old woman who presented with multiple nodules limited to the face. The diagnosis was based on the anamnesis, physical examination, and laboratory findings.

Case Report

A 90-year-old woman came with a chief complaint of mass on the face in the last one year. Initially, a small mass developed below the right jaw which enlarged accompanied by the occurrence of new lumps. The mass was pruritic and painful upon palpation and did not bleed easily. There was no fever nor general weakness, but the patient reported weight loss. There was no history of a mass in the neck, axillae or inguinal fold. The patient reported a history of lump surgery on the lower right jaw. There was no history of hypertension and diabetes mellitus. The vital signs were within normal limits. No lymphadenopathy was observed. Dermatologic examination showed multiple nodules on the face along with the presence of an immobile, firm nodule with irregular surface accompanied by smooth scales on the right mandible and left temporal.

Fig.1.C.

Fig.1.D.

Fig.2.A.

Fig.2.B.

Figure 1.(A,B,C,D) Initial presentation.
 Multiple erythematous and hyperpigmented nodules,
 along with an immobile and firm nodule
 with irregular surface on the right lower jaw accompanied
 on the facial region

The results of the complete blood count, random blood glucose, bleeding and clotting time, and liver and kidney functions were all within normal limits. Chest x-ray examination did not show metastasis. Histopathological examination of the mass on the face showed normal epidermal layer with shortened rete ridge. In the dermis layer, there was a proliferation of cells originating from lymphocytes with twice the size of mature lymphocytes with an oval, round nucleus, hyperchromatic, and prominent nucleoli which are evenly distributed. On the peripheral areas, lymphoid follicles with clear stratum germinativum were seen, supporting a cutaneous lymphoma. The immunohistochemical (IHC) examination showed positive for CD20 (B-cells) and CD3 (T-cells).

Figure2.(A,B) Histopathologic examination showed:
 a.Normal epidermis layer and tumor nest
 in the dermis layer
 b. Lymphoid follicleswith stratum germinativum

Fig.3.A.

Fig.3.B.

Figure 3.(A,B) Immunocytochemistry examination showed positive CD20 staining

The patient was then consulted to the Hematology and Oncology Department for chemotherapy. The first cycle of chemotherapy was planned to be administered for three days. The regimen used was R-CHOP (Rituximab - cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, vincristine, and prednisone). Unfortunately, the patient developed an anaphylactic reaction marked by the occurrence of shortness of breath and generalized erythema. Intravenous 10 mg diphenhydramine and 5 mg dexamethasone were thus given. After the reaction has subsided, Rituximab was withdrawn, and the administration of cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, vincristine, and prednisone was continued.

After finishing the second chemotherapy cycle, marked clinical improvement was noted, and the patient was eventually discharged. Nodules in the lower jaw reduced in size, leaving superficial erythematous ulcers. Chemotherapy was planned for a total of 6 cycles with 21 days interval between each cycle.

Discussion

PTCL is a group of lymphatic malignancies that occurs mainly in the skin and is the second most common extranodal Hodgkin

Fig.4. Immunohistochemical examination showed brownish colour on IHC examination using CD3 antibodies which indicate a positive result

Fig.5.A.

Fig.5.C.

Fig.5.B.

Figure5.(A,B,C) The clinical manifestation after the first cycle of the chemotherapy. Multiple erythematous and hyperpigmented nodules on the face with a giant immobile, firm nodule with an irregular surface in the right lower jaw, ulcer, accompanied by scales.

Figure 6.(A,B,C) Patient after the second chemotherapy cycle. Nodules, including the giant nodule on the lower jaw and frontal reduced in size, leaving superficial erythematous ulcers.

Fig.6.A.

Fig.6.C.

Fig.6.B.

lymphoma. Extranodal non-Hodgkin's lymphoma occurs in about 27% of cases and most commonly involve the gastrointestinal tract and skin.[1],[5] The infiltration of malignant lymphocytes characterizes cutaneous lymphoma into the skin.[6]

We report a case of CD20-positive CTCL in a 90-year-old woman based on the history taking, physical examination, and laboratory findings. CTCL is twice as common in men as in women.[6] The incidence of CTCL increases significantly with age, with an average onset between 50 and 60 years old and a four-fold increased incidence in patients over 70 years.[9]

The symptom observed in this patient was limited to the skin with no other organ involvement. By the literature, PTCL that leads to CTCL or CBCL is a non-Hodgkin lymphoma limited to the skin without extracutaneous involvement at the time of diagnosis. [2]

The patient was diagnosed with CD20-positive CTCL based on the positive immunohistochemistry results. CD3 along with CD5 and UCHL-1 is an antigen for T- cell markers [4] while CD20 along with CD19, CD 22, and CD 79a are monoclonal antibodies specific for B-cells.[10]

CD20-positive CTCL is very rare with less than 40 cases reported where the involvement of the skin manifests as skin plaque, nodules, or erythematous spots, without anyone particular predilection. CD20-positive CTCL is characterized by the co-expression of CD20 and T-cells markers.[4] CD20 is a specific marker in both benign and malignant B-cells. Therefore, this antigen may assist in distinguishing neoplasms originating from T-cells or B-cells.[10]

The patient was given CHOP regimen for three days. This regimen is the standard gold treatment for non-Hodgkin's lymphoma and consists of intravenous cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, and vincristine as well as oral prednisone. [11] According

to the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) guidelines, CHOP regimen is indicated for patients with anaplastic large cell lymphoma / ALCL (+), ALK ALCL (-), PTCL Not Specified Species (NOS), Angioimmunoblastic T-cell lymphoma / AITL, Enteropathy-associated T-cell lymphoma / EATL, MEITL, nodal PTCL and Follicular T-cell lymphoma / FTCL.[12]. CHOP regimen can also be administered to patients with diffuse large B-cell lymphoma. Savage et al. found that 78% of patients taking CHOP chemotherapy were patients with CTCL. This study also found that CTCL patient had a good response with a complete response rate of 89% and 5-year overall survival of 78% [13]. Rituximab is added to the chemotherapy regimen due to its CD20-specific action. Rituximab can kill CD20 cells directly due to their cytotoxicity and indirectly by inducing structural changes, apoptosis, making the cancer cells sensitive to chemotherapy.[14]

Similar to other monoclonal antibodies, the incidence of hypersensitivity reactions caused by rituximab has shown to be high. [15] In this case, the administration of rituximab led to an anaphylactic reaction. Rituximab was eventually stopped, and the patient was given intravenous 5 mg dexamethasone and 10 mg diphenhydramine.

CD20-positive CTCL is classified as PTCL-NOS with less than 20% 5-year survival rate.[3] Even with treatment of systemic chemotherapy and stem cell transplantation, CTCL NOS still has a poor prognosis.[16] There were no statistical differences in survival found among cases of either solitary/localized lesions or generalized skin lesions.[2] Because cutaneous lymphoma occurs on the skin, It requires skin care similar to chronic conditions such as eczema. Skincare needed includes maintaining skin moisture, bath with warm water instead of hot water, using soap with moisturiser, using detergent without fragrances, avoiding sun exposure and using sunscreen [17].

Conclusion

One of the most common forms of T-cell lymphoma is cutaneous T-cell lymphoma (CTCL), a general term for T-cell lymphomas that involve the skin. CTCL can also involve the blood, lymph nodes, and other internal organs. The diagnosis requires the integration of clinical, histopathologic and Immunohistochemistry (IHC) examination. A multidisciplinary approach to treatment and for patients with disease limited to the skin, expectant management or skin-directed therapies is preferred, as both disease-specific and overall survival for these patients is favourable. Multiagent chemotherapy (R- CHOP) provides a clinical improvement in this patient.

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